

**THE PLACE OF SAMARKAND NEIGHBORHOODS IN THE
ECONOMIC LIFE OF THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE**

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Abstract

In this article, the inhabitants of the city of Samarkand after its conquest by the Russian Empire, their occupation, the entry of Russian capital into the city and the development of capitalist relations in the city of Samarkand are expressed. In the sources of this period, additional information is given about the level of consumption of the inhabitants of Samarkand and their occupation of a certain profession.

Key words: Trade, capitalism, expedition, neighborhood, quarter, empowerment policy, statistics, district.

Абстракт

В данной статье выражаются жители города Самарканда после его завоевания Российской империей, их оккупация, вхождение в город русского капитала и развитие капиталистических отношений в городе Самарканде. В источниках этого периода даются дополнительные сведения об уровне потребления жителей Самарканда и занятиях ими определенной профессией.

Ключевые слова: Торговля, капитализм, экспедиция, соседство, квартал, наделение властью, статистика, махалла.

Introduction: During the Russian Empire, the city of Samarkand had a special place in the social and economic life of the Turkestan Governorate. The study of the land of Turkestan and its transformation into a base of raw materials began even before the conquest of the Central Asian khanates. Major-General Verigin's letter to Nicholas I (1825-1856) stated as early as 1826 that Central Asia is a source of cheap raw

materials and a convenient market for Russian goods. In the letter, Verigin explains his thoughts by saying that Russian products cannot compete in European markets due to their low quality, and that Central Asia, which cannot compete with Russian products, is very important for their sale [10; 72]. Samarkand will not be ignored as a result of this policy. Although the study of the city of Samarkand began before the conquest of the Khanate, its continuous and systematic study began with the creation of the Zarafshan district.

Literature analysis and methodology: The sources involved in the research process are mainly the literature of the period of the Russian Empire, and the sources of this period are distinguished by the fact that they are mainly based on statistics and the study of the economic life of the local people is given priority. The fact that the analyzed sources and the information presented in them are confirmed by the competent state bodies and management structures increases the level of reliability of the given information.

Result: General Abramov[6;18], head of Zarafshan district, was assigned the task of comprehensive study of the city of Samarkand. The goal was the economic appropriation of Samarkand, which is considered the central part of Turkestan, whose name has become a legend, and to subjugate it to the interests of the empire. For this purpose, General Abramov sent A.P. Fedchenko, who was studying the Fergana Valley (1868-1870), to Iskanderkol, a mountainous part of Samarkand in 1870[9;3]. The fact that Iskanderkol is a part of Turkestan rich in precious minerals caused General Abramov's efforts. The sending of A.P. Fedchenko, who has extensive experience in the population, ethnography, geography and history of the region as a result of carrying out geological research in the western part of Ferghana and Turkestan, means that great results are expected from this expedition.

Discussion: In this period, the majority of the population of Samarkand was engaged in irrigated agriculture and had a lot of experience. Professor A. Petsol was brought in 1871 for the purpose of researching the size of Samarkand's arable land and agriculture. Although A. Petsol's researches are mainly related to agriculture, his information is relevant for research. 4]. At the same time, not only the city of

Samarkand, but also its uezds are covered in detail in his scientific research. The reason why we call the scientist's research detailed is that his information is published in print, and information on each field is presented in a separate form. It is the first time that the distances of neighborhoods, guzars and villages from the city are given in a clear form.

Since 1906, accurate data on the population of five districts of the city of Samarkand has been brought to the Util during the Empire period. According to these data, at the beginning of the 20th century, 9,220 yards and 50,692 people lived in the part of the city of Samarkand inhabited by local residents [1;6]. However, it should not be forgotten that the strategically important cities began to consist of two parts - Asian and European parts. In order to create a base of its power in the colonial territories, the tsar's government brought many people of European nationality from the metropolis (Colonial Center) on the basis of various privileges or by force. It is this aspect that caused the change of the cities of Turkestan, including the city of Samarkand, not only in appearance, but also in terms of ethnicity and administration. At the beginning of the 20th century, in the European part of the city of Samarkand, there were 946 courtyards, and their number was 15,974[1;7].

The city of Samarkand, whose population consisted of 25-30 thousand people in the middle of the 19th century, turned into a unique metropolis of Central Asia with a population of 66 thousand people by the beginning of the 20th century. We can explain that the reasons for this are the increase in the number of the local population based on the stable situation, the increase in the number of immigrants, and the strengthening of trade and economic relations based on modern means of production. In some sources in the source studies of the imperial period, it was mentioned that the industry entered Turkestan as a result of the invasion of Tsarist Russia. Based on the conclusions of today's modern research, it can be said that capitalist relations existed in the land of Turkestan. But his roots were weak. The needs of the next period could create the ground for its rapid development. It was during the Tsarist period that the European part of the city of Samarkand began to establish modern means of production and enterprises. However, this had little positive impact on the lives of local residents. Because, firstly, they were not established in places inhabited by local people,

secondly, local people worked there as ordinary workers and received low wages compared to Europeans, and thirdly, most of these factories and factories were based on primary processing, and the products were transported to the central cities of the Russian Empire. they were brought to Turkestan as finished products and sold at high prices.

During the period of Zarafshan district, large-scale scientific research was conducted on the study of the ethnography and geographical location of the city of Samarkand or the former Samarkand province, as well as the potential of mineral and raw materials. These studies were not only a scientific study of the country, including the city of Samarkand, but also a study of the living conditions of the local population and, on this basis, strengthening the foundations of their long-term chain of rule.

In the researches of the imperial period, there are mentions of the families brought from Herat who were engaged in tailoring in the city of Samarkand and their neighborhoods. Being skilled tailors and weavers, they tried to meet the needs not only of the residents of Samarkand, but also of other cities and even foreign countries. About the arrival of the people of Herat to Samarkand, the following information can be found in the sources of the empire period. "During the Emirate period, 150 sewing and weaving families from Herat were moved to Bukhara" [8; 110].

Marv people were mentioned as another minority nation that played an important role in the economic life of Samarkand during the Zarafshan district. During the restoration of the city of Samarkand, they were promoted by Amir Shahmurad and were considered skilled craftsmen. A.D. Grebinkin interpreted the Marvites as a layer, a branch of the Iranians[8;112]. The similarities in their dialect, commonalities of life, and cultural life, although Grebinkin points out that the conclusions are correct, for long periods of time, Turkic or Turkicized people here The settlement of the peoples requires extensive research on Grebinkin's conclusions. Marvs and Iranians consist of around 1,000 families in Samarkand province, where gardening is especially well developed [8; 113].

In the 17th century, some Arabs from Afghanistan settled in the vicinity of the city of Samarkand, and their main occupation was blacksmithing [8; 185]. In the period

of Zarafshan district, information was also given about the life of peoples and clans such as Mazan, Luli, Juchi, Khoja in the city of Samarkand and its surroundings. They could also be found in 32 volosts of Samarand uezd [12; 38]. Since their main occupation is begging (mainly Luli, except for the Khuja clan), they constantly move around without settling down in one place. They mainly lived in Samarkand city in separate and small neighborhoods, engaged in small handicrafts and partly trade. Grebinkin spoke in detail about the social and economic characteristics of these peoples, and noted that they were given to local residents as barshchina (forced labor) to work, and this situation was especially widespread in the city of Samarkand and Chelak regions [8; 115].

When talking about the concept of industry mentioned in the sources of the empire, it is worth noting that in this period, the industry in the city of Samarkand was somewhat better developed than in other cities of the Bukhara Emirate. Innovations came from foreign countries through trade relations and were applied to production. The needs of the city's residents are met. However, the shortage of some raw materials, such as iron, steel and copper, made the industry of Samarkand dependent on foreign products. As a result, modern products were not produced. Therefore, the economists and historians of the empire that conquered Samarkand reported that there is no industry in the city, and everything looks very primitive. Tourist Marcoza Ye. When he came to Samarkand together with his companion Shamutdinov, he witnessed the Samarkand industry. Seeing that each stall is based on a specific product, he came to the conclusion that markets are orderly but chaotic. According to the tourist, weaving was dominant in the industry of Samarkand. In his memoirs, he informs that "the aspect that surprised me was the presence of craft workshops near every store and the quick preparation of the order" [7; 270].

After the invasion of the Russian Empire, many foreign companies, plants and factories were established in the city of Samarkand. As a labor force, people were brought from abroad and from the central regions of the Russian Empire. Local residents were involved in heavy and health-damaging work for a small wage. As a result of the development of capitalist relations and the entry of Russian capital into

Turkestan, local craftsmen and artisans, who were devastated, were forced to work in Russian industrial enterprises, even if it was cheap to earn a living. As of 1891, the following industrial enterprises, plants and factories belonging to Russian and foreign persons were operating in the Samarkand region. 19 trade-industrial enterprises and their agencies[11;11], 35 stores, shops and warehouses[11, 12], 2 hotels[11;13] were operating. In some of these, the local bourgeoisie also had shares, which did not amount to a large amount.

In the sources of the imperial period, some confusion arises due to the fact that statistical organizations have not yet been fully formed. For example, statistical reports and information of tourists are not similar to each other. The above information reflects the state of industry in Samarkand in 1891. However, it did not comment on heavy industry at all. In the tourist information of 1870, there are opinions about the presence of heavy industries in the areas of Samarkand city, where local residents are used as cheap labor. For example, in 1870, there were 12 cast iron, 4 brick, 34 oil, 30 tannery, and 2 soap factories in the city of Samarkand [4; 25]. These confusions make it necessary to conduct a number of scientific studies on the same issue.

The construction of the Kaspiyorty railway from Krasnovodsk to Samarkand in 1888, and the Samarkand-Andijan railway in 1898 closely connected the city with the southern parts of the Russian Empire and the major cities of the country, while Russian industrialists and investors actively entered Samarkand. created a great opportunity to bring agricultural products and other raw materials grown in the region to Russia. Departments and shops of dozens of trade and industrial companies engaged in transporting products from the region to the metropolis began to operate in the city and uezd of Samarkand. They have 117 stores in the city of Samarkand, and they mainly deliver cotton, silk, rice, livestock products, fresh fruit, wine, leather, agricultural products from the city to Russian cities, and Russian manufactured products to the residents of the region. those who are poisoned. Samarkand was the largest wine-growing center in Turkestan, and horticulture and viticulture were widely developed in and around it[3;373]. Since this development and existing material resources should

serve the interests of the empire in the future, the colonial officials did not stop studying the city of Samarkand from an ethnic and demographic point of view.

In the data of 1872, an Indian neighborhood of 100 people was mentioned in the city of Samarkand [7; 211]. The Indian citizens who lived here were mainly engaged in trade, usury and medicine, and made their due contribution to the development of the socio-economic life of the city. Afghans, estimated to be about 100 people, also had their own neighborhood in the city of Samarkand [7; 211]. In the sources of this period, it is noted that Afghans engaged in trade and directly or indirectly participated in Afghanistan-India trade. The imperial sources do not provide exact figures on the demographic status of Afghans. Because their main occupation was trade and seasonal work, most of them did not live permanently. The quoted figure does not show the exact number of Afghans living in the city. In fact, their number was more than 100[5;15].

The new urban part of the city will become ethnically diverse as a result of the active expansionist policy of the Russian Empire and the rapid development of capitalist relations. As a result, separate streets of those who came to power began to emerge. In the data of 1891, the following information is given on the ethnic composition of the population living in the new urban part of the city of Samarkand. In the European part of Samarkand today there are Russians-3233, Uzbeks and Tajiks-303, Jews-177, Germans-113, Tatars-85, Armenians-70, Iranians-66, Poles-65, Persians-20, Georgians-18, Kyrgyz 14, Lithuanian-8, Greek-7, Slovak-6, French-4, Mordovian-3, Finnish-3, Belgian-2, Romanian-1, Moldavian, Kumyk, Lezgin, Estonian, Chinese, Swiss, Bohemian and Afghans - 1 out of (8) - a total of 4206 representatives of foreign nationalities live [11; 92].

Summary: The neighborhoods in Samarkand city and region are covered in detail in the information of the empire period. Facts about the residents of the neighborhoods and their occupations are given. However, in this process, personal names and opinions about the cultural life of the population were almost never confirmed. The main attention is focused on the ability of the population to pay taxes (kurbi), their attitude towards the metropolis (colonial center). The statistics on the number of the population

also show that such research is based only on economic interests. This situation requires extensive research on these aspects. And it is necessary to pay attention to the aspects mentioned in these studies, to show the level of reliability of the data, and to mention the accuracy of the sources in the research process.

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